

The algorithm as the interface between the law and the code: the case of the Italian election of a regional parliament

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Abstract

We discuss the role of the epistemic difference between the algorithm and the software in the field of computational law, both in general and in a concrete case study. We report about a research and experimentation conducted in partnership with public administration during the electoral process that in November 2025 renovated the members of the regional parliament of one of the largest Italian regions. The partnership included an analysis of the text of the election law under the perspective of algorithmic thinking and the implementation of a software to be used to get precise early insights on the election outcomes.

We put forward the concept of *algorithmic normativity*, illustrating how the legal language can productively interoperate with the digital language through the abstraction level distinctive of the algorithm. In particular, we show how the electoral algorithm acts as a 'boundary object' that opens up a space for dialogue where legal advisors, administrative agents and ICT experts collaborate for addressing interpretation gaps and administrative issues, relying on this artefact as a shared comprehension of the electoral procedure. By considering the complexity of coordinating the different public institutions involved in the electoral process, we highlight the intrinsic non-neutral nature of the software, that cannot be thought of in isolation from the process in which it is inserted. We then hint at potentialities of computational law in electoral systems, remarking that a quality digital transformation is first of all a matter of transforming socio-technical processes made of a mix of people and tools.

Keywords: computational law; election law; algorithmic thinking; software development; socio-technical systems; cross-disciplinarity

1 Introduction

In the cross-disciplinary field of computational law informatics is mainly seen as a provider of technological solutions and applications, from concrete tools such as software, platforms or datasets, to abstract tools such as (AI) algorithms, domain-specific programming languages or knowledge models. Much less attention has been dedicated to the epistemic aspects and the scientific methodologies distinctive of this discipline. This bias depends partly on the fact that practical outcomes have an highly effective and immediate value that overshadows other aspects, and partly because computer scientists are not acquainted with epistemic aspects of their work, thus undermining the cross-disciplinary fertilization. Without delving into the depth of philosophy of science, a simple (and simplistic) way to refer to the epistemology of informatics is resorting to the so-called computational thinking, that is the set of conceptual and methodological elements that characterise the work of computer scientists

[1, 2, 3]. In this article we emphasise two of these elements, discussing their relevance for the field of computational law, both in general and in a concrete case study.

The first is the epistemic difference between algorithm and software, which is roughly the difference between the logic of a computation and the machine instructions that execute such a logic. In computer science it is well known [4] that keeping the separation between these two levels, and properly managing each one, is of paramount importance for plenty of motivations (e.g., correctness, security, maintainability, efficiency, clarity, liability) that have a clearly relevant counterpart in legal systems. An algorithm and a software belong to very different abstraction levels, but they are often confused or blurred for pragmatic reasons. We think that properly engaging in the analysis of this distinction in concrete cases, often neglected simply for time reasons, might have a relevant impact in computational law. The second element of computational thinking we highlight is a widely acknowledged lesson of software engineering: a piece of software cannot be separated from the socio-technical process in which it is inserted [4, 5, 6]. Accordingly, workflows, organisational procedures, personal habits, human relationships between different offices, as well as the very specific kinds of data that are at stake, influence the actual *effect* of a given software, which is much more than its *output*. This is especially relevant when there is a pressure for digital transformation, such as in the case of legal technologies for the public administration.

In this article we show these two epistemic aspects at work in a concrete case study that involves computational, legal, political and sociological elements. We report about a research and experimentation conducted in partnership with public administration during the electoral process that in November 2025 renovated the members of the regional parliament and the president of the government of Venetia, one of the largest Italian regions. The partnership has been appointed by the Regional Council of Venetia (*Consiglio Regionale del Veneto*), that is the public institution directly involved in the election. It included an analysis of the text of the regional election law under the perspective of algorithmic thinking, and the implementation of a software that computes the seats allocation given the citizens' votes. More precisely, the seats allocation procedure prescribed by the text of the law has been analysed and reformulated in an algorithmic format (using a structured natural language), precisely exposing the sources of interpretative doubts as well as the gaps between the textual description of the allocation logic and its manual operationalisation embedded into the official templates of the election records. Then the algorithm has been implemented into a software, that has been used during the actual ballot counting process to get precise insights on the election outcomes and manage the public communication of the Regional Council without waiting for the official results, whose manual computation and legal certification requires few days.

The clear separation between the algorithm and the software proved to be of fundamental importance in this case study. The algorithmic version of the textual law acted as a 'boundary object' [7, 8] expressing the logic of the seats allocation in a way that properly interacts both with the political nature of this process and with its intricate practical execution. The algorithm has been the constant bridge between the law (with related legal interpretations), the electoral records to be manually filled by poll workers, and the software to be automatically executed. As a consequence, the algorithm acted as an interface also between different people: the quirks of the seats allocation procedure described in the law have been conveniently expressed in algorithmic terms so that their graphical, textual, verbal and computational representations could be customised to make election laws's quirks accessible to politicians, administrative executives, legal experts, ICT experts, communication managers, journalists and citizens. A regional election is a complex and fragmented process that requires the coordination of many public institutions (municipal, regional and national administrations), hence having a cornerstone on which pivoting the management of the political, legal, administrative and technical aspects

of the seats allocation procedure proved to be very useful.

Moreover, the collaboration with the Regional Council of Venetia during the actual running of the election gave us the possibility to internally observe this process and test its permeability to elements of computational law. This experience put forward the relevance of many human factors in the process, mainly in the interfaces between computational and administrative operations and in the communication between different public institutions. As an example, the software that computes the seats allocation requires the correct numbers of citizens' votes, but the correctness and even the precise format of the required input proved to be a fragile node of the election process. Even the public communication had to cope with the introduction of the new software, searching for a balance between the transparency of exposing a lot of new fine-grained data and the need for effectively convey the (political) meaning of these data.

This case study illustrates that the digital transformation of public administration is mainly not a matter of introducing innovative tools, but rather a question of gradually transforming processes. The goal of the transformation should not be innovation per se, nor workflows should be changed to be simply adapted to new digital tools. Instead, a wise digital transformation starts by considering the rationale for a given process, e.g. the election process, so to identify the digital solutions that best suits the gradual reshaping of the organisational procedures and the management of the data at stake. The toolkit of informatics, ranging from technological solutions to methodological approaches, is clearly very useful, but it is essential to adopt a socio-technical perspective, acknowledging the non-neutral nature of any piece of technology [9].

We structure this article by first describing in Section 2 the case study, which consists in the algorithmic analysis of the text of the regional election law and the usage of a corresponding software during the actual ballot counting process. In Section 3 we then delve deeper into the role of the algorithm: we illustrate how it has been useful to clarify some interpretation gaps and, by conceptualising the difference between algorithm and software in terms of their different affordances, we put forward the notion of algorithmic normativity to highlight the specific impact of algorithmic thinking on computational law. In Section 4 we analyse the insights that the development of the seats allocation software provided on the socio-technical nature of the election process. We devote Section 5 to the description of the possibilities that this case study has opened up, distinguishing three areas of potential developments: electoral legislation, administration of the electoral process and digital tools to empower the management of electoral data. We finally conclude in Section 6 making a comment on the elements that in this case study favoured a fruitful cross-disciplinary dialogue between people with so different expertises.

2 Case study: the Italian election of a regional parliament

Election law is a subject that intertwines legal, political and mathematical aspects. The core of any election system is a procedure that determines the election winners given the votes expressed by citizens. Democratic elections require this procedure to be (at least) well-defined, transparent, and correctly executed, where the meaning of these three requirements spans both the legal and the mathematical scopes. Given this intrinsic double nature of the seats allocation procedure, it represents an interesting topic to be studied under the lenses of computational law [10, 11].

Mathematically speaking, any election procedure is a deterministic algorithm that takes citizens' ballots as input and outputs the names of the elected candidates by following a precise sequence of computation steps (e.g., electoral thresholds, majority bonus, proportional allocations). However,

given the textual nature of the legal system, the 'legal definition' of this procedure might not directly correspond to a clear-cut 'mathematic-algorithmic definition' [12]. We remark that, differently from other cases where the substantial expressivity of natural language is at the heart of the legal protection [13], the computation of an election procedure should minimise the interpretation gaps. Counting machines and other tools for electronic voting have been often advocated to prevent errors and frauds due to manual computation, but they have proved to actually shift the problem to errors and frauds that are hidden within these tools that are more difficult to inspect [14, 15, 16]. Informatics has much more to give than technologies and tools, and by recognising the algorithmic nature of the seats allocation procedure, we can resort to that field of computer science that deals with algorithms as conceptual artefacts independent of technologies.

Under this perspective, in 2025 we started a partnership with the Regional Council of Venetia (*Consiglio Regionale del Veneto*), which is the legislative institution of one of the largest Italian regions, to conduct an algorithmic analysis of the text of the law that defines the mechanism to elect the members of the regional council and the governor of region. This election mechanism¹ has a medium level of complexity: it includes coalitions of parties, the possibility to cast a disjoint vote for a candidate governor and a separate coalition, a non trivial electoral threshold, a majority bonus, and an iterative process of seats distribution -first between coalitions, then between parties, then between constituencies- carried out with subtly different proportional methods.

2.1 The algorithmic analysis of the text

The goal of the initial analysis was to highlight the algorithmic structure of the seats allocation procedure, that is given in Article 21 and in Article 22 subsections 3-7 as a sequence of textual paragraphs. The legal text has been reshaped into a numbered sequence of simple *algorithmic instructions* of the following kind (see Section 4 for an example):

- each basic instruction is made of a single sentence written in natural language (Italian) whose length is possibly no more than one line;
- structured *for-each loops* are used to repeat a uniform list of basic instructions for each candidate or for each coalition or for each constituency. The syntax of for-each loops, made of an initial clause that marks the number of repetitions (e.g., for each candidate) and an indented list of simple instructions to be repeated uniformly, highly improves the clarity of a procedure, which is visibly formatted but still written in natural language;
- complex operations, such as filtering according to the electoral threshold or applying the majority bonus, are packed into a single instruction that calls a dedicated *sub-routine*. Factoring the procedure into sub-routines breaks the sequentiality of the control flow in the execution of the instructions, but administrative agents non expert in informatics had no problem in dealing with sub-routines since they are similar to the familiar mechanism of an hypertext;
- every instruction is written referring to a minimal set of basic concepts that have a fully precise definition within the text of the election law. These building blocks are the vote counts, both local and regional (namely, '*cifra elettorale regionale e circoscrizionale*') of each candidate governor, of each candidate councillor, of each list, of each coalition.

¹Legge regionale del Veneto 16 gennaio 2012, n. 5 (BUR n. 7/20 1 2) "Norme per l'elezione del presidente della giunta e del consiglio regionale".

The resulting algorithm consists in a list of 20 instructions with additional 7 sub-routines, each consisting of about 10 instructions but for a complex step (Article 22 sub. 6) which required 42 instructions. Besides formatting the instructions to emphasise the procedure's general structure, a relevant choice has been to always explicitly refer to the building blocks mentioned above. Indeed, even if Article 22 sub. 3 and 4 precisely define the vote counts concepts, the text of the law sometimes adopts synonyms or terms that only implicitly refer to these concepts². This operation of rephrasing any computation step in terms of explicit references to the suitable vote counts exposed a number of gaps in the interpretation of the law, that have been addressed by referring to the jurisprudence with the help of the Regional Council's administrative officers and legal advisors. Interestingly, one of these gaps had been the object of a legal controversy in past elections³, but we found room for other possible interpretations. In absence of legal certainty, we decided to parameterise the algorithm according to the intended interpretation by adding an instruction of the kind 'if the legal interpretation is ... then do ... else do ...'.

We postpone to a later section the discussion about the algorithm and the role played by this artefact during the electoral process, and we move to the illustration of the software that the Regional Council requested to automatically execute the seats allocation algorithm.

2.2 A software to get a view on the election outcomes

Having a rapid and automatic way to compute the results of the election from the citizens' ballots, enables a lot of interesting possibilities: before the election it can be used to simulate the effects of different political strategies for candidates and coalitions, whereas during the election it can be used to get quick insights on the outcomes and the possible issues of the seats allocation. These advantages were clear to the administrative officers, which asked for a software under the control of the Regional Council, without having to rely on the outcomes of the off-the-shelf software provided by the national Ministry of the Interior.

With the help of a professional programmer we then implemented the seats allocation algorithm into a stand-alone Java desktop application named *Psephos*, in reference to the small stones used in the ancient Greece to cast votes. The internal logic of the software directly reflects the modular structure of the algorithm and its data model is shaped around the basic building blocks corresponding to vote counts. We remark that the design of the structure of internal data is a key choice in a software, thus anchoring this choice on elements that have a clear correspondence in the text of the law increases the reliability and the accountability of the tool.

While the implementation of the internal logic of *Psephos* posed no challenges thanks to the previous accurate study of the election algorithm, the management of input and outputs revealed sensitive issues. Input data consist in the citizens' vote counts collected from the regional territory, that initialise the corresponding data structures of *Psephos*. The region is divided into 4.729 polling stations partitioned into seven constituencies; the poll workers manually count the votes and communicate the numbers to the local municipality. These numbers are immediately sent to the national Ministry of the Interior, which publishes them as unofficial data, while the reports compiled by the polling stations are collected and validated by the regional Court of Appeal, which in few days proceeds with the allocation of seats and the legal certification of the election outcomes. Our software gets input data from the public service offered by the Ministry of Interior, which updates the vote counts every few minutes as

²Interview with legal experts explained that in legal drafting this happens for stylistic reasons and might also be the result of successive updates of individual paragraphs of the law.

³In the regional election in 2020 there has been a controversy in distinguishing a coalition made of a single list from a list not part of any coalition.

long as the percentage of counted polling stations increases. At each percentage, Psephos computes the corresponding seats distribution and the final composition of the regional parliament. Therefore, the software's input critically relies on the Ministry's service, and its output is actually relevant only when the percentage of counted polling stations is significant and the final seats distribution stabilises.

In the development of Psephos we experienced difficulties in connecting with the digital service provided by the Ministry, mainly depending on the fact that the logic of that service is hardwired into a software written by an external provider. The technical difficulty in connecting two softwares reflected into a difficulty in the interaction between the offices in charge of those softwares, revealing the complexity of the coordination between different public institutions, each made of many internal branches with well established praxes.

Moreover, running Psephos during the actual regional election day, hence under the public and political pressure to which the regional council was subjected⁴, manifestly showed that the output of a software is never just a piece of data: any number produced by Psephos was perceived as a political fact, its output interface had an impact on the perception of the overall trend of the ongoing election, and the incremental nature of its computation –which advanced according to the percentage of counted polling stations– raised the sensitive question about when and how to communicate those incremental data to the press.

Precise details and a comprehensive discussion will be developed in Section 4, where we emphasise the intrinsic socio-technical nature of any software, that cannot be thought of in isolation from the context in which it is inserted and from the reactions of people populating this context.

3 The algorithm as a boundary object

In initial discussions the administrative managers of the Regional Council were interested in software technologies that allow for a precise oversight of the seats allocation process. In previous elections the early outcomes were manually computed (using spreadsheets) through statistical projections made by domain experts, therefore they wanted to complement these projections with fine-grained automatic early computation of the final composition of the regional parliament. However, after illustrating the relevance of precisely capturing the logic of the seats allocation procedure and the advantages of decoupling the algorithm from the software, the managers welcomed the proposal of starting with a preliminary algorithmic analysis of the text of the election law. A crucial role in shifting the interest from the software to the algorithm has been played by the ability to rephrase in cross-disciplinary terms the well known insights developed by software engineering [4]. In particular, we highlighted the human-readable nature of the algorithm, that lays at an abstraction layer that is intermediate between (i) the text of the law, (ii) the text of the instructions and reports for poll workers, and (iii) the machine-consumable code. Therefore, the algorithm is the appropriate layer to grasp the political meaning of the mathematical operations that proportionally distribute the seats, and to expose the subtle interpretation gaps related to these operations that are present in the text of the law.

In other terms, the algorithm acts as a 'boundary object' [7, 8], that opens up a space for dialogue where legal advisors, administrative agents and ICT experts collaborate for resolving those gaps, using this artefact as a shared comprehension of the electoral procedure. This in turn leads to more legal (and political) certainty, simplification of the templates of the electoral offices' records and transparency and correctness of the corresponding software. In the language of organisational studies

⁴The author had been officially appointed to the scientific committee of *Osservatorio Elettorale del Consiglio Regionale del Veneto* and the real-time usage of Psephos to provide quick and detailed overview of the election outcomes had been publicly announced to the press by the Regional Council one week before the election day.

[17, 18] the algorithm supports the coordination of different 'communities of practice' and favour the sharing of the so-called 'tacit' dimension of knowledge, that is embedded into practices rather than being explicitly codified. Indeed, acting as a boundary object between different communities, it makes explicit the need for negotiation between diverging interpretations, prompting each community to reconsider its practices, assumptions, perspectives and presuppositions [19].

As a concrete example, consider the text of the electoral law prescribing the electoral threshold for coalitions:

*"Coalitions that have obtained less than 5% of the total valid votes are not admitted to the allocation of seats, unless they are composed of at least one [party] that has obtained more than 3% of the total valid votes expressed in favor of the lists."*⁵

This text has to be converted to a sequence of operations that poll workers have to officially record. In particular the operationalisation of the text requires to clarify the meaning of "total valid votes" and "total valid votes expressed in favour of the lists". This is not trivial because the law admits complex valid patterns of votes, where a citizen can cast a vote for a party and/or a vote for one or two candidate councillors and/or a vote for a candidate governor possibly associated to a coalition that does not include the chosen party⁶. We then rephrased the text as the following algorithm (which is a sub-routine of the seats allocation algorithm), where every computation depends on the basic building blocks corresponding to the vote counts of each coalition and party, that we remind are the sole terms precisely defined in the text of the law.

Algorithm for Electoral Threshold

INPUT: $count_c_i$ and $count_p_j$ vote counts of each coalition and party
 $tot_votes = count_c_1 + \dots + count_c_N$
 $tot_lists = count_p_1 + \dots + count_p_M$

- 1 $T_coalitions = (5 \cdot tot_votes) \div 100$ rounded up
- 2 $T_lists = (3 \cdot tot_lists) \div 100$ rounded up
- 3 **repeat for each coalition c :**
- 4 **if** $count_c \geq T_coalitions$ **then** c is admitted
- 5 **otherwise:**
- 6 find the party p in the coalition c with highest vote count
- 7 **if** $count_p > T_lists$ **then** c is admitted
- 8 **otherwise** c is not admitted (since all its parties are under T_lists)

Compared to the corresponding manual operations prescribed in the electoral record, this algorithm is much shorter. This depends partly on the fact that in the algorithm the computation to be done for each coalition is written only once as the body of a for-loop, whereas the template of the record contains a long sequence with the same computation copied-and-pasted as many times as there are coalitions. Moreover, the algorithm checks the threshold of at most a single party within each

⁵We used the term 'party' instead of 'group of lists' to simplify and avoid mentioning the difference between lists and groups of lists. The original text of the law is: *"Non sono ammesse alla assegnazione dei seggi le coalizioni che abbiano ottenuto meno del 5% del totale dei voti validi, a meno che siano composte da almeno un gruppo di liste che ha ottenuto più del 3% del totale dei voti validi espressi a favore delle liste"* (Article 21).

⁶More precisely, the regional election law combines two elections into a single ballot: the election of regional councillors between the candidates of different lists, and the election of the president of the regional government between candidates associated to different coalitions of lists. This double election in a single ballot with cross-party voting is the source of many difficulties, especially in the description of the voting options, both for the citizens and for the polling workers that have to identify nullified votes to properly compute vote counts.

coalition, whereas the record prescribes the computation of the percentage of votes of all parties of all coalitions.

Summing up, on one side there is the short and involute text of the law, on the other a lengthy⁷ template of election record that exposes many details. The algorithm lays in the middle: it is detailed enough to be directly executable for computing the coalitions admitted to seats distribution, and it is written in a compact and structured format that easily allows to reason on the political meaning of the distinctive threshold mechanism chosen by the regional election law.

Additionally, the discussions with administrative officers and legal advisors about the precise definition of "total valid votes" and "total valid votes expressed in favour of the lists" revealed a major interpretation issue in presence of a coalition made of a single party. This happened to be a political open issue, then we decided to keep open all the solutions; pragmatically, we recast this specific issue in terms of the difference between the 'coalition vote count' and the 'party vote count' (see the variables *tot_votes* and *tot_lists* in the input lines of the algorithm above), and we made the general algorithm parametric with respect to the selected interpretation. Notice instead that the instructions for poll workers and the template records they have to fill cannot be parametric, and they are indeed printed according to a specific interpretation. In the regional election in November 2025 no coalition made of a single party came across this problem, but running Psephos with different parameters gave the Regional Council the possibility to check on the fly that the election outcomes did not change under different interpretations, thus increasing the confidence on the early seats allocation⁸.

3.1 From code-driven law to algorithmic normativity

In the field of computational law there is a lot of attention to so-called 'rules as code' approaches (RaC), where legal norms or policies are articulated in computer code at different scales [20, 21, 10, 22, 23]. We think that shifting the focus from software technologies to algorithmic thinking would bring on new insights.

For instance, an interesting way of conceptualising the difference between algorithm and software is observing that they entail different affordances, intended as the action possibilities that arise from the relations between the artefact and the environment [24, 10]. Indeed, the environment of a human-readable algorithm more naturally entails relations with people, whereas a software tends to draw more attention to its outcomes than to the internal functioning. A precise account of this conceptualisation needs thorough consideration and is beyond the scope of this article. Moreover, we acknowledge that many aspects distinctive of algorithms have been already considered in the literature about code-driven law, in particular where computation is advocated to clarify the logical structure and the coherence of norms and regulations, hence to support legislation drafting and contestation. However, we claim that by framing these aspects under a terminology that keeps open the distinction between algorithm and software helps in identifying the advantages and the limits of many computational approaches to the legal system. In line with the spectrum of RaC normativity presented by McBride and Diver in [10], we put forward the concept of *algorithmic normativity* based on the specific affordances of algorithms, which is intermediate between the legal normativity based on text-driven legality and the opposite technological normativity based on code-driven legalism [11, 12].

⁷In the official record of the 2025 election the section devoted to the electoral threshold is 10 pages long and considers 5 coalitions and 14 parties.

⁸Instead, in the official record of the past regional elections in 2020 the Court of Appeal adopted an official statement to update the interpretation of this issue. The text of the law however has not changed after that statement, then the question is still open and up to the legislative power of the regional parliament.

In the case study of the regional election, the features of the algorithm that played a relevant role were two: its human-readable language and its structured logic. A well designed modularity provided for clarity, separation of concerns, and the ability to move from the global view of the seats allocation procedure to the local functioning of specific steps, and back. These features, that are completely independent of any software, enhance *(i)* the political reasoning about the election mechanism, *(ii)* the improvement of the textual description of the election law, and *(iii)* the simplification of the electoral records. We already mentioned the handling of the electoral threshold, but the algorithmic analysis revealed other issues: an entire sub-paragraph of the law⁹ is devoted to deal with a case that can actually never happen, moreover, the different proportional methods adopted in the hierarchical process of seats distribution –first between coalitions, then between parties, then between constituencies– prescribe the adoption of mathematical adjustments that can in principle be problematic. The administrative agents were not aware of these subtle aspects of the election law, and we planned an in-depth study of the electoral technicalities for training the Regional Council’s officers and improve future election processes.

We finally point out that a relevant difficulty of working at the algorithm level is the choice of the language to express algorithmic instructions, which may range from a pseudo-code near to a domain-specific programming language up to a simple itemised list of instructions in natural language. This choice requires to find a suitable trade-off between precision and simplicity, which highly depends on the use case and its environment. In the case of the regional election we adopted the structured language described above in order to emphasise the modular logic of the seats allocation procedure and to keep the instructions close to the terminology adopted in the election law, but other choices are possible. Software engineering developed insights and best practices on this topic (e.g., model driven development, flow-charts, business process modelling techniques [25, 26, 27, 4, 28]) whose connections to legal systems deserve to be further investigated, also taking into account the various legal markup languages that have been already developed [29, 30, 31]. However, the main point is that, differently from software languages, the algorithmic thinking intends to keep a flexible human-readable nature, permitting to adapt the language of the algorithm to the expertise of the intended reader. Additionally, it might sometimes be useful to produce multiple artefacts that express the same algorithm in different language styles and at different levels of precision. Indeed, in the case of the seats allocation we produced other two versions of the very same algorithm: one refined (with hints on underlying data structures) for ICT experts that had to implement the corresponding software, and one simplified and more coarse-grained for public communication. Clearly, adopting multiple versions of the same algorithm at different abstraction levels introduces the problem of correctness, but this flexibility proved to be effective in achieving an inclusive cross-disciplinary dialogue between people with very different roles.

4 The software as an element in a socio-technical process

A software, intended as a tool that instructs a machine, is commonly seen as a technical artefact that transforms inputs into outputs, where the role of people is to properly design, build and operate the artefact. Looking at a software just in terms of inputs and outputs hides the process that led to that specific design compared to other possibilities, moreover the assumptions for its usage and the intended meaning of its output often remain implicit. These elements, that depend on a mix of technical, organisational, social and also contingent factors, are important in the construction of the software, but once in production they are usually left behind, focusing on the results produced by the

⁹The final sentence of Article 22 comma 6.

tool. However, these elements are relevant in determining the actual impact of the software on the environment in which it is deployed, since its usage produces outcomes and effects that are beyond its outputs. The non neutral nature of technical artefacts is well known in philosophy of science [9, 32, 5], but struggles to penetrate common perception, especially among IT professionals and computer scientists. Instead, an increased sensitivity to the socio-technical component of, even simple, digital artefacts would be helpful in the cross-fertilisation between computer science and law, especially in public administration, where there is a pressure for digital transformation pushing toward the adoption of 'innovative' tools.

In the case study of the regional election the digital artefact is technically rather simple: the software Psephos is a medium size¹⁰ standard Java software that makes simple mathematical computations according to the (not simple) logic prescribed by the election law. However the introduction of this tool in the general election process enabled a number of effects that were only partially expected. Some of these effects depended merely on the presence of the new software not even on its actual running. Indeed, its development triggered an inquiry and an inspection of several administrative procedures, which in turn provided for a grasp of the fragmentation of these procedures, and became a test of the permeability of public institutions to elements of digital transformation in the interface between the administrative and the technological apparatus.

More precisely, any software needs to be inserted in a larger system that *(i)* feeds the input, *(ii)* hosts the software execution and *(iii)* collects the output for the intended usage. For Psephos, the input (i.e., data about citizens' ballots) is provided by a digital service of the national Ministry of the Interior, its Java code is executed on a laptop under the responsibility of our experimental project, and (a subset of) its output is sent via email to the Regional Council IT division for public communication. Therefore running this software combines the actions and the responsibility of different offices and different administrations.

Connecting Psephos with the Ministry's digital service required a retro-engineering effort from a sample of data related to the past regional election since no official documentation was available. An interaction with the ministry's agents revealed a critical issue in their software related to a problematic counting of the ballots that cast a double vote for a party and a disjointed candidate governor. We remark that this issue had been gone unnoticed for long time because the logic of this service is hardwired into a software written by an external IT provider, hence the connection between politically relevant elements and data structures is blurred into the digital code which is difficult to interpret for people in the Ministry with no digital skills. On the contrary, we let the building blocks of Psephos to be precisely anchored to the human-readable algorithm.

Fixing the technical problem and connecting Psephos with the Ministry's digital service exposed the complexity of coordinating different public institutions (the national Ministry, its external provider, the Regional Council and the Regional Government) and people with different roles, both administrative and IT. In this complexity, sociological elements like personal trust, motivation, well-established practices and attitudes toward responsibility and oversight merge with organisational procedures and workflows [33]. Moreover, these interactions exhibited the entangled management of the entire electoral process and the difficulties coming from the fact that many agents have only a very partial view of the entire process. This fragmented nature of the election process and of the network of people involved challenges the fluidity of the flow of data and information. As acknowledged by organisation science, the organisational context shapes knowledge and learning [19], and the current coordination of the (electoral) process in terms of offices and administrations makes the integration of the (elec-

¹⁰Approximately 7.650 lines of Java code, of which 1580 are for executing the algorithm's logic, the others are for input validation and output presentation.

toral) knowledge more difficult compared to the adoption of a perspective based on the coordination of working practices [19]. In this view, the algorithm's role as a shared boundary object that activates dialogue among different working people might also be relevant in developing a process-oriented view of the electoral practices, that might help recompose part of the intrinsic fragmentation.

In this scenario, the toolkit of digital systems and their methodological practices can be helpful to carefully and gradually transforming the current well-established practices and workflows and bring in clear advantages, but this is possible only by combining tools and engineering techniques with a socio-technical evaluation, that takes into account the human factors and the vicissitudes of real world application of legal technologies [11].

Another element of any software that is particularly exposed to human factors is its interface, which is indeed a subject of the human-computer interaction research domain. In the case of Psephos we designed a simple graphical user interface to display the vote counts of each candidate (both governors and councillors) and each party, and the distribution of the seats between parties and constituencies (hence both the political and the territorial distributions of seats). The final graphical visualisation and public communication of these outputs was up to the IT branch of the Regional Council through the institutional website, whereas the output interface of Psephos was intended to be used internally by the administrative managers to have a clue of the election outcomes during the phase of ballot counting. Approximately every five minutes Psephos connected to the Ministry's service to input updated vote counts and immediately displayed the seats distribution corresponding to the current input. The interface then showed the percentage of the counted polling stations corresponding to the most recent input and also allowed to tune the legal interpretations of the subtle issues identified during the algorithmic study.

Before the election we discussed the question about at which percentage of counted polling station which data computed by Psephos had to be disclosed to the public press. Clearly the election outcomes require the completion of the vote counts, as well as their legal certification, but an early look to these outcomes might disclose strong hints on political results in presence of distinct margins between competing parties. The sensitivity of this aspect was clear, both at the political level and at the public communication level, then during the press conference that one week before the election announced the usage of this software we emphasised the incremental nature of its computation and the corresponding need to properly interpret the data, even if that data would have been announced at a high percentage of completion. However, all the reflections and cautions that were clear before the election took on a different nuance on the election day in front of the ballet of numbers displayed on Psephos interface. Under the political pressure of an electoral count, even a partial and temporary number triggers emotional reactions, political narratives and thoughtful inquiries about the political effects of the mathematical proportional methods prescribed by the law.

This experience shows how introducing a tool that makes available a lot of fine-grained data generates the requirement of managing the meaning of those data, that is deciding which one to expose and think about how to prevent their misinterpretation. In other terms, the introduction of a tool that generates fine-grained data should be paired with the introduction of mechanisms and professional skills to oversee the connection between the technical and the non-technical meaning of these data.

5 A space of possibilities for transforming processes

The pilot project we carried over in collaboration with the Regional Council of Venetia opens up a broader study of the electoral matters under the lenses of computational law. We distinguish three

areas of potential developments: the evolution of the electoral legislation, the improvement of the administrative process involved in elections, the upgrade of Psephos (or similar tools) to empower the political and mathematical analysis of electoral data.

5.1 Electoral legislation

Any electoral law contains a section that describes how to map citizens' votes to the final seats allocation, and we already underlined that this is actually an algorithm. Thus thinking to the seats allocation directly in algorithmic terms and resorting to the toolkit of algorithmic thinking would support legal drafting in writing the text of this section of the law still in natural language but in a more clear and precise way; we could even think to add to the law an appendix that displays (parts of) the algorithm written in a structured way, similarly to what happens for the facsimile of the image of the ballot paper, that is textually described in an article of the law, but its depiction in appendix is essential for its comprehension [12]. This in turn leads to the already mentioned question about the choice of the suitable language for writing an algorithm to be included in legislation, but we think that there is space for fruitful research and experimentation, since flowcharts or simply structured texts are already adopted in legal systems, especially in regulations.

Another major benefit that algorithmic thinking would bring to electoral legislation drafting would be the development of tools that enhance the comprehension of the seats allocation procedure under draft, in particular the understanding of the political meaning of specific combinations of mathematical operations. Indeed, in our case study we realised that the distributional effects of the mathematical computation prescribed by the law were not entirely clear to political candidates; this is not surprising due to the complexity of the iterative seats distribution mechanism. Therefore, it would be very useful to empower the legislator with a way to interactively run simulations to compare, analyse and tune the effects of each element of a modular algorithm, for instance figuring out the effects of different combinations of electoral thresholds and majority bonus under different scenarios.

5.2 Electoral administrative process

The advantages and the limits of digital technologies in the organisation and workflows of the public administration are largely studied. In the specific case of the regional election process a wise and accurate usage of digital solutions offers in particular a substantial opportunity to improve the templates of the election records and the corresponding instructions that poll workers have to follow. We already illustrated the example of the simplified computation of the coalitions passing the electoral threshold, but in our case study we identified a number of other possible simplifications. Moreover, great advantages could come from the introduction of even very simple digital checks on the results of intermediate computations, as well as from the automatic filling of parts of the record that should be simply copied from a previous section. In the case of the Italian regional election we came to know that some of these possibilities are already implemented by digital tools that support electoral offices, but each public institution involved in the process seems to have its internal tool to handle its specific portion of the global electoral mechanism. Sharing this knowledge and letting the different tools interoperate would clearly be of great advantage for the whole system, since at present the only point where common information converges are the long and involute textual reports. Anyway, harmonising the work of the electoral offices of the Regional Council, the Regional Government, the national Ministry of the Interior and the regional Court of Appeal is a long and difficult road, where technical and human factors are intertwined.

5.3 Electoral tools

Many digital tools can be envisioned to empower the electoral system, and we already stressed the need to look at them under the perspective of the socio-technical environment in which they are inserted. Drawing from our experience, we highlight two major elements of our approach: the role of the accurate algorithmic analysis preliminary to the software implementation and the fact that we made a bespoke work instead of adapting a commodified solution. These factors have been essential for instance in the discovery of the issue in the digital service that the Ministry outsourced to the external IT provider. Errors, flaws, imprecisions and simplifications normally happen, but when they are hardwired into machine code they risk to go unnoticed, whereas if the logic of that machine code is made human-readable and is precisely linked to its legal meaning, then many more people are able to check and supervise. For instance, an administrative officer spotted an issue in the way we modelled the majority bonus in the electoral algorithm, witnessing the importance of this logical artefact that acts in the boundary of different expertises.

The tailored approach that we adopted in this project is clearly not scalable, but significant advantages can come from small changes thoughtfully conceived and carefully engineered. As an example, we plan for future work to develop a tool to help reading a ballot with cross-party votes: indeed, even if the voting modalities are written in the text of the law and exemplified in the instructions for poll workers, different visualisations and interactive checks might be of great help both for the voting citizen and for the correctness of the vote counts. Moreover, the modular architecture of Psephos makes it smoothly upgradable to run electoral simulations based on statistical forecasts.

6 Conclusions

In this article we discussed the cross-disciplinary research and experimentation conducted in partnership with a regional Italian parliament during the election that renewed its councillors. The central aspect of this case study has been the development of a fruitful dialogue between experts with different skills: digital, legal and administrative. The first step in this direction has been finding a suitable level for common understanding of the electoral matters. The concept of algorithm proved to be appropriate, both to frame the discussions about the political and the executive aspects of the election law, and to build an artefact that fruitfully acted as a boundary object between people with different roles in the electoral process. On that account we put forward the concept of algorithmic normativity to characterise the impact of the algorithmic thinking (and related epistemic methodologies distinctive of informatics) on legal systems and to differentiate it from the so-called rules as code normativity [10] that is rather oriented towards technologies.

The second element that favoured the cross-disciplinary dialogue has been considering the digital artefacts as elements inserted into a socio-technical context. Under this perspective, in the article we exposed the difference between algorithm and software in terms of their different affordances, intended as their different effects on the environment. We illustrated how during the election day the software for computing the early election outcomes mediated both action and perception [34] of administrative agents, acknowledging that the meaning of a program cannot be reduced to a purely technical question [35]. Considering the complex interdependence of the different public institutions involved in the electoral process, we hinted at potentialities and limits of computational law in electoral systems, remarking that a quality digital transformation is first of all a matter of transforming socio-technical processes that incorporate a mix of people and tools.

To conclude, we mention the importance of experimentation for the cross-disciplinary training of professionals. Drawing from our experience, we hint at the skills that would be useful to improve.

From one side, digital literacy of legal and administrative agents should include (even simple) logical modelling, algorithmic thinking and software engineering methodologies. On the other side, the education of IT professionals and computer scientists should enhance their awareness about epistemic aspects of informatics and increase their sensitivity to the non-neutral, socio-technical, aspects of digital artefacts. Empowering an effective dialogue between so different skills is essential to sustain a carefully engineered and wisely enacted transformation of processes within public administration.

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